

METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING LEXICAL COMPETENCE IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract: this article shows that Methodology of developing lexical competence in preschool education. Besides, there are many ways are written for developing lexical competence in preschool education

Keywords: Children with foreign roots, multicultural and multilingual, Brazilian residents in Japan, vocabulary assessment, conceptual vocabulary, narrative

Recently, the number of children with foreign roots has been increasing in the settings of early childhood education and care and developmental support. Their families' national origins and first language are also diversifying (e-stat, 2019). These children grow up in a bilingual environment and speak their first language and Japanese. Many of their parents cannot communicate fluently in Japanese. Therefore, childcare and social workers face difficulties communicating with these children and parents. Childcare and social workers need to have an appropriate understanding of the developmental status of children. However, in the case of bilingual children, one of the biggest challenges is understanding the actual situation of their language development.

In most cases, monolingual children have well-balanced skills between verbal comprehension and verbal expression. However, in the case of bilingual children, there might be a large developmental gap between verbal comprehension and expression skills. A lot of bilingual children can understand what others say but nevertheless cannot express themselves effectively. In addition, the learning speeds of Japanese and that of the heritage language are not the same. Children are more likely to learn and use a language spoken at home. Such a developmental gap between two languages or different language skills brings about difficulty in evaluating the actual status of language development in bilingual children.

Another factor that hinders the accurate evaluation of language skills in bilingual children is the use of reference values obtained from standardized tests designed for monolingual children. It is inappropriate to use such values to calculate the developmental ages and indexes for bilingual children. Needless to say, if children whose mother tongue is not Japanese receive assessments in Japanese, it will never be possible to capture their potential. As Shimoida pointed out, such standard values should be treated just as references. Therefore, it is difficult to obtain specific figures such as developmental ages and quotients for bilingual children. The factors

of cultural differences and parental socioeconomic status also hinder the accurate understanding of language development in bilingual children.

Nevertheless, to identify and support the potential of preschool children with foreign roots, the assessment of language development is critical. Otherwise, they may not receive necessary help at the early childhood stage and may fail to fully develop their abilities at school due to the language barrier. Furthermore, according to a previous study the vocabulary and narrative skills of preschool children in their heritage language could affect the future progress of language learning at school. Therefore, in my current research study, I seek a methodology to evaluate the status of language development, in particular the vocabulary development of young children who grow up in a bilingual environment. I am also pursuing studies to ascertain whether reading aloud to children in the heritage language can improve children's ability to retell the story in Japanese. In this article, I will discuss some results of my research.

Studies on children's vocabulary development

First, I will introduce some studies on the assessment of vocabulary development in children. According to previous studies conducted by researchers in Europe and the US, children who were raised in a bilingual environment (in particular, those from families of lower socioeconomic classes) were more likely to exhibit delayed language development (Bialystock et al., 2010; Uccelli & Páez, 2007). Some researchers in English-speaking countries proposed the use of a measure of conceptual vocabulary to evaluate vocabulary development in children who grow up in a bilingual environment (Pearson et al., 1993). The theory of a conceptual vocabulary is that, if a child receives a vocabulary test in two languages and answers correctly in at least one language, the child is deemed to have the concept of the word. By using this assessment method, underestimating children's potential to acquire vocabulary knowledge can be avoided.

However, there are certain issues to consider when applying a measure of conceptual vocabulary to bilingual children using Japanese and another language. For example, the Japanese word "*miru*" has several corresponding words in English, such as "look," "watch," and "see." Or one may even wonder if there is another appropriate translation. It seems that there are not many words that have exactly the same concept in two languages. In particular, highly abstract words such as adjectives and verbs are more difficult to match the concept in two languages compared to nouns that refer to concrete objects. In my current research project, the theory of conceptual vocabulary to assess children's vocabulary development has been employed. After considering the above shortcoming, I determined to conduct a vocabulary test in Japanese and Portuguese^{*3} using nouns with specific meanings.

[Assessment]

For vocabulary assessment, I used a Brazilian Standard Expressive Vocabulary Test consisting of 100 questions asking the names of pictures shown to children. The Portuguese-speaking staff conducted the vocabulary test in Portuguese, and the Japanese-speaking staff conducted the vocabulary test in Japanese, respectively.

All in all, the vocabulary data of the above ten children were also analyzed to find any correlation between their Japanese/Portuguese vocabulary and Japanese MLU/TDW. As a result, it is confirmed that a stronger correlation was found between Portuguese vocabulary and Japanese MLU/TDW. Therefore, although it is too early to reach a conclusion until sufficient data analysis is completed, children's vocabulary in their heritage language may affect their ability to retell a story in Japanese

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